

MEDICAL SCIENCES

POSSIBLE ERRORS MADE AT THE DIAGNOSTIC STAGE OF PROSTHETICS

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Abstract

Restoring the chewing function aims not only to replace lost or damaged teeth, but also to restore the trajectories of movement of the lower jaw. These trajectories are strictly individual, and depend both on the anatomical shape of the tooth crowns and on the shape of the temporomandibular joints.

Due to improper orthopedic treatment, carried out without taking into account the peculiarities of the relationship of the dentition, changes occur in the temporomandibular joint, which leads to arthritis, arthrosis, headaches, and discomfort when opening the mouth. Even before the emergence of orthopedic dentistry as a separate specialty, doctors tried to restore as much as possible the basic functions of the masticatory apparatus in patients with tooth loss. At the same time, the problem of insufficiently accurate diagnosis in dentistry has been and remains relevant today. During orthopedic treatment of patients, it is important to restore the occlusal relationships equally accurately both in the oral cavity and in the dental laboratory on models. To do this, to help the dentist and dental technician, special equipment was created in the form of an articulator and a facial bow. These devices help in solving various clinical and laboratory issues in the manufacture of dentures, as they take into account the anatomical features of the dental system of each individual patient.

Keywords: *articulator, facial bow, diagnostic stage.*

Currently, mechanical articulators are devices that allow for primary diagnostics of plaster models, diagnostic wax modeling, production of all types of dentures, splints, treatment control, etc.[1]

Plastered diagnostic models make it easier to make a diagnosis and develop a plan for the patient's dental rehabilitation, and help monitor its results. Plaster models located in the interframe space of the articulator can be documented by photography, which provides additional advantages in visualizing the original situation.[3]

However, when working with articulators, it is necessary to take into account certain parameters to minimize inaccuracies that accumulate and lead to various types of errors.

At the diagnostic stage, when working with mechanical articulators with a facebow, errors may occur when:

- obtaining impressions of the dentition, surrounding structures and creating plaster models;
- registration of central occlusion, central ratio;
- transferring the position of the upper jaw using a face bow;
- placement of models in the interframe space of the articulator, etc.

Accordingly, in such cases, the analysis of the position of the lower jaw, static and dynamic occlusion studied in the articulator, will be incorrect, since the

movements of the lower jaw are carried out along trajectories that are not typical for a given patient.[4]

At the stage of creating plaster models of the dentition, it is important to initially obtain high-quality impressions using metal non-perforated trays. To a greater or lesser extent, the impression is deformed during removal from the mouth and also has the ability to recover to varying degrees. Therefore, it is desirable to use modern materials with the least shrinkage and the greatest ability to restore dimensional stability, such as polyvinylsiloxanes and polyesters. The impression material should be selected taking into account the clinical situation. In cases of tooth mobility, alginate may be the material of choice.[2,5]

When cured, such gypsum has less expansion and greater resistance to abrasion than other gypsums when the technology is followed. Superhard gypsum powders should be strictly dosed and mixed with water in vacuum mixers. The resulting plaster model should be characterized by high homogeneous density, strength and accuracy of reproduction of teeth and surrounding structures. Plaster expansion, which is not always taken into account, also leads to significant errors. When plastering diagnostic models into the interframe space of the articulator, it is necessary to use articulation plaster, which, with strict dosing, quickly hardens and has the least shrinkage, although it is fragile in structure.

The correct position of the upper jaw model in the interframe space of the articulator relative to the reference plane is important. One known method of transferring the position of the upper jaw relative to cranial landmarks into an articulator is a facebow. However, the arbitrary hinge axis is not the true axis of rotation of the condyles, and therefore the transfer of the position of the maxilla with a standard facebow can be considered to some extent arbitrary. Ideally, the axis of rotation of the heads of the lower jaw when transferring the model of the upper jaw into the articulator should coincide with the hinge axis of the articulator. But this is not always possible, since the ear canals can be located at different levels, i.e. not be symmetrical, and the position of the heads of the lower jaw may not be central, but shifted. The positioning of the patient's head during the application of the face bow is also important. In addition, in patients with dysfunctions of the temporomandibular joints, determining the hinge axis is difficult and sometimes impossible. This problem can be partly solved by electronic axiography and searching for the kinematic axis.[6]

It should be noted that it is important to use the articulator and facebow from the same brand, as otherwise this may lead to diagnosis and treatment planning relative to different landmarks.

The facebow frames should be oriented relative to the stated reference plane and its location relative to the horizon should be controlled. It must be taken into account that the right and left halves of the articulator are symmetrical, therefore, incorrect placement of the arch on the patient's head can lead to the orientation of the face bow at an angle to the horizon and subsequently to the tilt of the upper jaw model.

Incorrect positioning of the upper jaw model will inevitably lead to incorrect positioning of the lower jaw model and, accordingly, to distortion of the occlusal relationships of the dentition. In the future, when adjusting the joint mechanisms of the articulator to an individual function, the trajectories of movement of the lower jaw will also be distorted.

Determining the physiological position of the mandible in the space of the patient's skull and transferring occlusal or interocclusal registration (central occlusion, centric relation) as the initial diagnostic position of the mandible in the space of the articulator are

also the key to successful diagnostic work. However, often when plastering the lower model to the upper one, according to the register of the position of the lower jaw obtained by the doctor, inaccuracies may occur. Accordingly, further diagnostic procedures will not be correct. Checking the accuracy of plastering of the lower jaw model according to the register must be checked on the upper jaw model. If a gap is found between the plinths of the upper model, the lower one should be knocked off and re-plastered according to the previously obtained register.

Conclusions

Probably, in the near future, real impressions, models and the need for their plastering will supplant virtual data transfer and computer planning, but at this stage real diagnostics and planning of the patient's dental rehabilitation are still relevant.

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